

INFLUENCE OF TRANSCRYSTALLINE INTERPHASE ON FLEXURAL FAILURE OF SHORT CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PEEK COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Two kinds of short carbon fiber reinforced poly(ether ether ketone) composites were prepared with and without transcrystalline interphase. The fiber length distribution, fiber orientation and crystallinity were all carefully characterized. These composites with thickness of 3 mm and span-to-thickness ratio of 32 were subjected to three-point-bending test at speeds of 0.5, 5, and 50 mm/min. The transcrystalline interphase enhanced the fiber-matrix adhesion, improved the flexural deflection and strength of the composite. The fractography was examined by means of scanning electron microscope. The appearance of load-deflection curves and the fractography suggest that the compressive crack occurred first; the stress concentration under the loading nose and the shear stress maximum induced the upper shear cracks which blunted the propagation of compressive crack. Then the tension crack initiated from the tension side, met with the lower shear crack near the core region, and resulted in a catastrophic failure.

KEYWORDS: PEEK, Injection molding, Transcrystalline, Flexure, Failure mode

INTRODUCTION

The most attractive features of short-fiber composites may lie in their potential for rapid, low-cost mass production and simplicity of manufacturing. Short carbon fiber (CF)/polyether ether ketone (PEEK) composites outperform samples/products made from the pure PEEK matrix in terms of stiffness and strength. CF improves the flexural deflection or the flexural crack resistance considerably. It is well established that the significant improvement in mechanical properties for reinforcement in semicrystalline polymers over amorphous polymers can partly be attributed to the morphology and crystallinity of the polymer matrix in the interfacial region. Fibers affect the matrix morphology in semicrystalline melts because the fibers can act as nucleation rods causing a structure known as transcrystalline. It is believed that transcrystalline interphase, a kind of "physical coupling," would enhance the stress transfer between the fiber and the matrix. It is still an open question, however, whether or not a transcrystalline layer around the reinforcing fibers in composites with semicrystalline thermoplastic matrices may improve the mechanical property profile [1-4].

The mechanical properties of these composites are dependent on several important microstructural elements, including fiber length, fiber volume fraction, fiber orientation, fiber-matrix interphase strength, and morphological features such as degree of crystallinity, spherulitic size, lamella thickness and crystallite orientation [5,6]. These features are, in turn,

affected by variations in the processing conditions, such as mold geometry, melting temperature, molding temperature, and the rheological properties of the molding compound. Information about the effect of the transcrystalline interphase on the macroscopic performance of long fiber-reinforced polymers with good fiber/matrix adhesion is available. Spherulitic and transcrystalline morphologies of injection molded fiber-reinforced samples are difficult to investigate because of preparation problems. The increased use of thermoplastics has brought about a need for better understanding of the processing techniques used to manufacture these materials.

In the previous papers [7-10], thermal stability experiments [7] have indicated that neat PEEK was stable in nitrogen up to the temperature of 400°C, holding for 15 min. This treatment was effective in reducing nucleation density to the point of allowing morphology control [8-10]. In this paper, attention is focused on the effect of fiber orientation and transcrystalline interphase on the flexural properties of the composites. Attempts have been made to study the flexural failure mechanism of short CF/PEEK composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Injection-molding grade composite pellets were ordered from RTP company under the trade name "RTP 2285." In this material, PEEK of grade 150 is fortified with 30 wt% short carbon fibers. The pellets were melted in a heated cylinder at 400°C and were injected at a mold temperature of 180°C or 120°C using a machine of conventional type (Engel ES 200/50). The samples have the following codes: 400/180, 400/120. The number before the slash (400) indicates the melted temperature at the cylinder and the number after the slash (180 or 120) stands for the mold temperature. The flexural bars of 127 x 12.5 x 3 mm³ (according to the ASTM D790 standard) were injection molded and carefully characterized in terms of the fiber orientation, core size, average fiber length, fiber length distribution and degree of crystallinity.

Specimens of 10 x 12.5 x 3 mm³ were cut from the center part of the bar. The transverse sections and the surfaces of the specimens were embedded in a phenolic resin and polished successively down to 0.05 µm aluminum oxide finish. Results on the fiber orientation and the core size across the bar thickness were established by reflected light microscopy (LM) of the polished surfaces. The fiber length distribution curves of five 6-10 mg pieces, cut along the thickness direction, were determined by transmitted LM after burning off the PEEK matrix at about 500°C under dry air flux in a thermogravimetric analyzer (Perkin-Elmer TGA-7). Randomly selected cross sectional views were photographed at an effective 100X magnification. The average fiber length of at least 350 fibers obtained from four to five pictures was measured statistically for each specimen. The overall crystallinity of the specimens across the bar thickness were detected by differential scanning calorimetry (DuPont 910 DSC) at 20°C/min heating rate. Both temperature and heat flow scales were calibrated with indium and lead at the same heating rate under a constant nitrogen flux.

The mechanical test used was the three-point-bending test with a span-to-thickness ratio (s/t) of 32:1. The plaques were tested at room temperature (RT) on an Instron universal testing machine (Model 1125) at crosshead speeds of 0.5, 5, and 50 mm/min, respectively. The deflection reading as a function of the applied load was recorded during the entire test until the applied load dropped substantially, as a result of internal damage in the specimens. The fracture surfaces of broken test bars were cold sputtered with a very thin layer of gold and were examined with a JEOL JSM 6400 scanning electron microscope (SEM) using a high voltage of 20 kV in the secondary electron image.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure Characterization

The molding-induced microstructure of the short fiber reinforced grades can be approached by the flow model of Tadmor [11] and Rose [12]. The shear and elongational flow field developed during the cavity filling process are responsible for the well-known 3-layer fiber orientation microstructure. The fibers were highly aligned to the MFD (mold filling direction) in the two surface layers, whereas fibers in the central layer were dispersed perpendicular to the MFD. The area of the central layer was 0.8% of the cross section in this study. The polished surface of 400/120 specimens showed a high value of fiber orientation. However, the short fibers showed an in-plane random distribution on the surface of the 400/180 specimens, which displayed five-layer structure across the thickness. The exterior layer was about 200~250 μm thickness. The velocity profile, at any fixed location, was maintained until the abrupt cessation of flow when the mold was filled. Upon the cessation of flow, relaxation of the melt [13] started and was followed by a disorientation of the fibers because the mold temperature at 180°C was beyond the T_g of PEEK (143°C).

The fiber length distribution of 400/120 and 400/180 specimens is expressed by L_w/L_n . L_n is the number average of fiber length, calculated by

$$L_n = \frac{\sum N_i L_i}{\sum N_i}$$

L_w is the weight average of fiber length, calculated by

$$L_w = \frac{\sum N_i L_i^2}{\sum N_i L_i}$$

No discernible difference of the average fiber length across the bar thickness was found among the specimens. The L_n for specimens molded at 120°C and 180°C were 118 μm and 107 μm , respectively. The corresponding L_w were 147 μm and 145 μm . The fiber length distributions (L_w/L_n) were 1.25 and 1.36, respectively.

All the DSC traces from various depths of the thickness of the 400/120 test bars showed the recrystallization behavior. The cooling rate of the central layer was also high at mold temperature of 120°C. There was no recrystallization at all in the case of 400/180 specimens. This indicates that the crystallization of the skin layer was completed in 30 s at 180°C during the holding and cooling periods of injection. The apparent fusion enthalpy was estimated by subtracting the exothermic recrystallization peak area from the melting peak area. This measure was quite inexact because the fusion enthalpy and the heat of crystallization per unit crystallinity were quite different near 170°C from that at 330°C [9,10]. The seventy percent of crystallinity of the composite is determined as the ratio of the apparent fusion enthalpy to the fusion enthalpy of a sample of PEEK with 100% crystallinity, taken as 130 J/g [14]. The crystallinities of 400/180 and 400/120 specimens are thus 28% and 24%, respectively. The latter was probably over estimated because of recrystallization [9,10].

Flexural Properties at Room Temperature

In the flexural tests of the 400/120 and 400/180 specimens at RT and at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min, the load increased up to an average deflection of 9.0 mm for the 400/120 specimens, and 11.4 mm for the 400/180 specimens. These deflections corresponded to the maximum stress level without any initial load drop and the load dropped off sharply as soon as the fracture was initiated on the tension side. This implies that the composite was very brittle without any crack propagation step at RT. Crack initiation was thus believed to be the dominant failure energy absorption process of fracture for $T < T_g$. The composite responses between the applied load and the deflection were quite linear in the first 3.5 mm, after which

the curves displayed nonlinearly. In the nonlinear region, failure mechanisms on a microscale (e.g., debonding at the CF/PEEK interface) were possible.

From the load-displacement curves, the flexural modulus and the flexural strength were calculated by using the equations of homogeneous beam theory. Table 1 lists the flexural modulus as a function of crosshead speed. The modulus in GPa for the 400/120 and 400/180 specimens, respectively, were found to be 24.2 and 21.9 at 0.5 mm/min; 24.2 and 22.3 at 5 mm/min; 24.9 and 22.8 at 50 mm/min. Each data represents an average of at least three specimens. A rise in flexural modulus of 400/180 specimen containing higher crystallinity is expected. However, data illustrated in Table 1 do not confirm this expectation. This can probably be ascribed to the higher fiber orientation of 400/120 specimen. Also, the modulus of the composites increases with crosshead speed, which is characteristic of the common strain-rate dependence of polymers. The modulus values obtained at RT ($<T_g$) give an indication of the global degree of fiber orientation, but do not reflect the degree of crystallinity.

Table 1 Flexural properties of short CF/PEEK composites versus crosshead speed. Three-point bending test ($s/t=32$) at RT.

Specimen code	400/120			400/180			
	Speed, mm/min	0.5	5	50	0.5	5	50
Modulus		24.2	24.2	24.9	21.9	22.3	22.8
GPa		(0.4)	(0.9)	(0.8)	(0.3)	(0.4)	(0.2)
Deflection		9.0	9.0	9.5	11.4	10.9	11.3
mm		(0.5)	(0.4)	(0.3)	(0.4)	(0.2)	(0.7)
Strength		334.1	338.6	359.0	356.2	357.5	375.7
MPa		(9.9)	(9.4)	(7.3)	(2.1)	(3.9)	(15.8)

The number inside the bracket, (), is the standard deviation.

The corresponding deflection and strength are also listed in Table 1. For all cases shown, the deflection of the 400/180 specimens was about 20% higher than that of the 400/120 specimens. The deflection values obtained at RT ($<T_g$) are seen not to be sensitive to percent crystallinity. Unlike the deflection, the strength of the 400/180 specimens was always slightly higher than that of the 400/120 specimens. The strength values in MPa increased sharply from a speed of 5 to 50 mm/min for both 400/120 and 400/180 specimens. The effect of crosshead speed was in the opposite direction to that observed for other neat polymer systems, i.e., a trend to brittle fracture with increasing strain rate. The major difference is considered to be due to crystallization on the carbon fibers, which possibly contain transcrystalline. At RT, flexural behavior is influenced by the microstructural parameters of fiber orientation and transcrystallinity in composites.

Fig. 1 SEM micrographs of the fracture surface of (a) 400/120, (b) 400/180 specimens tested at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. The scale bar corresponds to 1 mm. Top and bottom edges are presented as black color.

Failure path and mechanism

The load dropped sharply at the maximum load, which corresponds to the tensile failure in the outer surface. This implies that the composite was very brittle and without any propagation step at RT. The SEM micrographs at longitudinal section through the center of the damaged 400/120 and 400/180 specimens, tested at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min, are presented in Figs. 1a and 1b, respectively. For both specimens the damage in the form of shallow crack appeared on the compression side just (about 250 μm) below the loading nose (arrow A in Figs. 1a,b), this shallow crack did not take place over the entire specimen width. One much deeper crack was recognized (arrow B in Figs. 1a,b) between the core and the shallow crack. SEM micrographs of a close view of both sides of the deeper crack at a tilt angle of 23° (one side was rotated 180°) are presented in Figs. 2a,b and 3a,b for a damaged 400/180 specimen tested at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The direction of plastic drawing (arrow direction) is opposite between the pair of the convex and concave parts, and the pair of the top and bottom sides of the crack. Shear cracks on the top and bottom sides were recognized from the opposite drawing direction of the matrix. Thus, the crack propagation on the top side is independent from the crack formed on the bottom side. The fracture surfaces show fibers surrounded by matrix material in both sides of the fractography. This indicates that the composite did not fail adhesively, but cohesively.

Fig. 2 SEM fracture micrographs of the convex part of the 400/180 specimen: (a) top side (b) bottom side. The specimen was tested at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The scale bar corresponds to 10 μm .

Fig. 3 SEM fracture micrographs of the concave part of the 400/180 specimen: (a) top side (b) bottom side. The specimen was tested at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The scale bar corresponds to 10 μm .

Significant damage including multiple shallow and deep shear cracks was found right after the load drop, indicating that the damage occurrence and growth were progressive in the initiation step. The 7.5 mm nonlinear region indicates that stable crack propagation constitutes the major part of the initiation step. The appearance of load-deflection curve and

the fractography suggest that the compressive crack occurred first. It is also suggested that the deep shear crack on the compression side occurred before the tensile crack initiated from the tension side. Based on the above observation, the shear cracks along the longitudinal direction through the center of the damaged specimen are sketched in Fig. 4. This flexural failure behavior is quite different from that of continuously unidirectional composites, where the tensile failure dominates at a span ratio of 32:1.

Fig. 4 Schematic of deep shear crack across the longitudinally damaged specimen.

SEM micrographs in Figs. 5 a,b,c and 6a,b,c show the fractured surfaces of PEEK reinforced by short CF at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. In particular, Figs. 5 (500X magnification) refer to sample 400/120 and Figs. 6 (3000X) to sample 400/180. As the load increased, elastic strain energy was accumulated in the specimen, then at large deflection, a large degree of fibers was pulled out quite cleanly on the tension side (Figs. 5c,6c). The crack propagated along the fiber-matrix interface and fiber ends, leaving bare fibers on the failure surface. No strong differences in CF/PEEK adhesion were evident on the tension side.

Bare fibers were also observed on the compression side for the specimens molded at 120°C (Fig. 5a). No marked difference in the extent of pull-out of the fibers was observed between the compression and tension sides. If the homogeneous nucleation is dominant and incomplete, impurities will be accumulated at the fiber-matrix interface and the interfacial bond will be weak [5,15]. This implies a poor bonding between CF and PEEK matrix with a fully spherulitic morphology in the 400/120 specimens. In contrast, the fracture surface for the specimens molded at 180°C showed fibers surrounded by a sheath undeformed matrix material (~1 μm) on the compression side (Fig. 6a). According to the 20% higher deflection and higher strength at break values (see Table 1), this is indicative of a strong bonding between the fibers and matrix which can be attributed to the presence of the transcrystalline interphase. The boundaries between spherulites and transcrystalline regions provided the weak fracture paths in the material because of the diffusion of low molecular weight and/or noncrystallizable fractions to the growing crystallization fronts [5,15].

In Figs. 5b and 6b, SEM micrographs of the core region show that fibers were embedded in the PEEK matrix -- cohesive matrix failure. It clearly indicates both good adhesion and insufficient matrix shear strength. The transcrystalline regions were found across almost all the fibers observed under higher magnification (3000X) in the cases of the 400/180 specimens tested at crosshead speeds of 0.5, 5, and 50 mm/min. For the 400/120 specimens, in contrast, an increase of speed from 0.5 to 50 mm/min resulted in a change from cohesive failure to adhesive failure. The results showed clearly that the occurrence of transcrystallization was dependent on the specimen cooling rate which was slower at higher molding temperature ($180^{\circ}\text{C} > T_g > 120^{\circ}\text{C}$) and in the core region. In the section of microstructure characterization, the 400/120 specimens showed the recrystallization behaviour in the core

region which indicated that the crystallization of the 400/120 specimen was incomplete during the holding and cooling periods of injection. The matrix shear strength was reduced at higher strain rate because the amount of amorphous PEEK was high. In the 400/180 specimens, the transcrystalline resulted in the 20% higher deflection and the corresponding enhanced strength.

Fig. 6 SEM micrographs of the fracture surface of 400/180 specimen: (a) compression side, (b) core, and (c) tension side. The crosshead speed was 0.5 mm/min. The scale bar corresponds to 10 μm . (Upper right)

There are several possibilities for the occurrence of the transcrystallization: (1) slow cooling after melting at high temperature to remove the nuclei [8,9]; (2) stress induced crystallization [16,17]; (3) the stresses induced by the difference in thermal expansion coefficients [18,19]. In the surface layer, the shear stress was maximum and the mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients was also maximum during cooling to the mold temperature. In the core region, the cooling rate was much slower than that in the surface layer because of the low thermal conductivity of PEEK matrix. A spherulitic pattern [20] was observed in the core of the 400/120 specimen after the flexural test at the speed of 5 mm/min. The spherulitic size within the matrix was estimated to be $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter. It took 24 s and 13 s, respectively, to grow this spherulite if the corresponding crystallization temperatures were 310°C and 305°C [8]. It implies that the nuclei surviving in the core were much less than expected and the cooling rate was slower, too. Therefore, it was possible to allow the growth of the transcrystalline layer in the core of the 400/120 specimens.

Three different fracture paths are possible [15]: (1) at the CF/PEEK interface; (2) at the interphase between spherulitic and transcrystalline structures; (3) through the PEEK matrix by cohesive failure. The arrangement of boundaries between spherulites and transcrystalline regions is dependent on the relative distribution of the two phases and on the strength of the interfaces between the two phases. It should be noted that it is now somewhat unrealistic to refer to the transcrystallized interphase and the spherulite matrix as the interphases now impinge on each other to form the major fraction of the matrix in the 400/180 specimens. These boundaries provided weak fracture paths in the material. In this study, direct evidence for better interfacial bonding of transcrystallinity to the fibers can be illustrated by the microscopy observation, as shown in Figs. 6a,b. Transcrystalline structure combined with good fiber/matrix adhesion changed the fracture path. A large amount of transcrystalline meant also an easier transfer of stress, and thus the materials are able to sustain large deflections before the break. Based on the above observation, the flexural failure path ($s/t=32$) is schematically presented in the figure of extended abstract for the 400/180 specimens tested at RT and at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min.

Now let us discuss the sequence of flexural failure. If the deep shear crack occurred first, the damaged portions of the specimen may continue to act as separate beams, and the energy absorbed in this section is rather low. Thus, the deep shear crack is not supposed to precede both compression and tension cracks.

Next discuss the sequence of compression and tension cracks. For the span to thickness ratio ($s/t=32$) used in these experiments, the flexural failure mode was expected to be of the tensile type (instead of shear failure). If the tension crack preceded the compression crack, the deep shear crack would be on the tension side and failed in Mode I where the direction of plastic drawing was parallel in both sides of the crack. This is in opposite to the observation. From the appearance of load-deflection curves and the fractography, considerable damage appeared on the compression side just below the loading nose, thus the compressive crack is suggested to occur first (denoted as #1 in Fig. 7). According to the numerical analysis, the first compression crack in the middle layer should start right under the loading nose because of the stress concentration [21]. It is possible that the initiation of the upper shear crack (denoted as #2 in Fig. 7) was a consequence of this initial compressive failure or of the maximum shear stress [22]. The compression cracks propagated downward, and interacted with the expanding upper shear cracks because the shear stress maximum also moved towards the core region. The inclination of the deep cracks also suggests the possibility of shearing action producing the cracks. The above discussion precludes the possibility of upper shear cracks originating from the lower tension cracks. Thus, compression crack and the upper shear crack preceded the tension crack in the bottom layer. The compression crack, associated with the

predeformation of the upper shear crack, caused the ductile failure with a corresponding large deflection of about 9-11 mm for injection-molded CF/PEEK composites.

The upper shear crack's propagation and further compression cracking were intricately related to each other. Compression crack away from contact zone was almost vertical. With further loading, the compression crack (#1) and the upper shear crack (#2) described above joined together to initiate a macroscopic fracture. The propagation of the compression crack was blunted by the upper shear crack. In addition, the upper shear crack did not take place over the entire specimen width. The s/t ratio, stresses and deflection of the composite would then be recalculated at the same load, and the propagation of the upper shear crack is restricted, too. The upper shear crack may also be stopped by the disorientation of the fibers near the core region [23].

Fig. 7 A schematic drawing of the failure sequence of the injection-molded CF/PEEK composites. Three-point bending test ($s/t=32$) at RT and at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min.

There are two possibilities regarding the relation between the lower shear crack in the middle layer (#3) and the tension crack in the bottom layer (#4). Either the lower shear crack appeared first, and stopped the upper shear crack from spreading sideways, or the upper shear crack itself diverted into the tension crack. In all of these tests, a tensile failure of the outermost fibers on the tension side was observed at the point where the maximum load was reached. During the loading up to catastrophic fracture, the shear microcracks induced matrix macrocracking and caused pull-out of the fibers from matrix. Thus the lower shear crack and the tension crack can be regarded as mutually exclusive events happening almost together. Direct evidence in producing these cracks is required. Based on the above discussion, the events (compression crack, upper shear crack, lower shear crack, and tension crack) leading to failure of the injection-molded CF/PEEK composites are schematically presented in Fig. 7.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a change of 60°C in the mold temperature (one above T_g and one below T_g) resulted in a change from a transcrystalline morphology to a spherulitic morphology. The transcrystalline interphase enhanced the fiber-matrix adhesion, improved the flexural deflection and strength of the composite. At the RT, the fiber orientation dominated the modulus. Multiple shallow and deep shear cracks were observed in the compression side of the damaged specimens. The compressive crack is suggested to occur first; the stress concentration under the loading nose and the shear stress maximum induced the upper shear crack which blunted the propagation of compressive crack. Then the tension crack initiated from the tension side, met with the lower shear crack near the core region, and resulted in a catastrophic failure. The transcrystalline interphase changed the flexural failure path and was able to sustain larger deflections before the break.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported financially by the National Science Council, ROC, under contract number NSC 87-2216-E110-011.

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